

Generation of Emergency Trajectories Based on Aircraft Trajectory Prediction

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Abstract—We present an automated emergency trajectory generator to compute the best emergency trajectory for a given landing site. A given emergency 2-dimensional (2D) path (i.e., route) is used as input for a trajectory predictor (TP), which computes a trajectory by taking into account the current aircraft performance and weather. The set of vertical profiles considered in the TP has been designed in order to cover the widest possible range of emergency situations. Moreover, the aircraft intents considered in these profiles are chosen by taking into account the operational requirements of the air traffic operation system and the input of the flight crew. A set of representative profiles has been tested during the study, to verify the result of the proposed algorithm and its computing time. Furthermore, the effect of the distance to go on the resulting trajectories has been also analyzed. This concept is expected to be part of an advanced flight management system on-board function to help the pilot take efficient and effective decisions in emergency situations and adverse conditions.¹

I. INTRODUCTION

Nowadays, emergency trajectories for airliners in a degraded flyability mode do not exist except for engine loss situations in standard instrumental departures (SIDs), for which airliners have to specifically design the corresponding flight procedure. The current process of defining emergency trajectories and landing sites remains completely manual and fully relies on the capabilities of the pilot for situation analysis. Still, for some specific emergencies, pilots can follow the recommendations—such as the recommended vertical profile for a depressurization emergency—that are detailed in each aircraft’s flight crew operating manual (FCOM), as there are no specific functionalities in the flight management system (FMS) for that purpose. In emergency situations, an automated support to the pilot could suppose a clear advantage by computing a trajectory to safely bring the aircraft from the location where the emergency takes place until a safe and appropriate landing site.

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We can observe in history several cases of successful landings with very degraded aircraft capabilities—e.g., the U.S. flight 1549, ditching in the Hudson river after a double engine failure caused by bird strike—in which, thanks to a good situation analysis of the aircraft crew, the safety of the passengers and integrity of the aircraft structure were preserved. However, in other situations the consequences were fatal and, even if the outcome is positive in some cases, having an automated emergency trajectory generator could help to ensure avoiding compromising the safety of the operation in abnormal situations.

In this work, we present an emergency-trajectory-generation function for commercial aircraft allowing a safer return to ground when normal operation is interrupted, in the context of future automated operations with reduced crew. The trajectory is generated with a trajectory predictor, where both the aircraft performance and the most updated weather forecast available are taken into account. A comprehensive list of vertical profiles—used when generating the trajectory—has been identified in this work, designed to be as generic as possible in order to cover the widest possible range of emergency situations. We choose a set of representative profiles from this list, and we show their evolution of both speed and altitude as a function of the distance to the landing site. In addition, we give details regarding the trajectory phases and set of aircraft intents involved for each of these representative profiles. Furthermore, we also show how the distance to the landing site could affect the shape of the resulting emergency trajectories. Finally, in this paper, we also present a trade-off analysis where we compare—by highlighting the strengths and weaknesses—several approaches that could be used to generate emergency trajectories, concluding in each case what is the option used in this work. Ultimately, the outcome of this work is to bring a support to the pilot—in both flight management and decision making—in emergency situations with degraded aircraft capabilities, where emergency trajectories would be injected within the FMS. In this work, we focus only on the generation of the vertical trajectory, assuming both a landing site and an emergency 2-dimensional (2D) path (i.e., route) to that landing site have been previously computed. In recent work [1], the process of generating this route was described.

In future work, an insight on the landing site selection process will be given, and a wider range of situations will be investigated in order to assess the feasibility of our concept.

Similar works have dealt with the generation of emergency trajectories for civil aircraft. For instance, in [2], the authors presented an automatic post-failure flight planning to enable safe emergency landings. More recently, in [3], the authors also investigated the problem of the generation of a safe landing trajectory for an airplane with structural damage to its wing and flying very close to local terrain. In [4], an emergency planning technique focusing on small aircraft was presented. However, in all these works, only one type of emergency was considered (i.e., loss of thrust), thus, neglecting the rest of possible emergencies that could happen. Similarly, in [5], trajectories were generated for a loss of thrust emergency, but only considering purely geometric criteria for the generation of the trajectory, thus, neglecting aircraft dynamics. Finally, other remarkable works considering path planning under an emergency can be found in [6], where road-maps are used to generate the path, or in [7], where a real-time flight trajectory generator was presented. Furthermore, Garmin Ltd. developed the Autoland system [8], exclusively dedicated to general aviation. It consists in an autopilot-based functionality which, in case of an emergency where the pilot is unable to fly, determines the most suitable airport and runway and leads the aircraft to that runway, by taking into account weather, terrain, obstacles and aircraft performance capabilities.

To the best of the authors' knowledge, although there are many works dealing with the generation of emergency trajectories, they are mostly based on the geometric planning of these trajectories. Furthermore, most of the existing works do not take into account the operational requirements of the air traffic operations system (or the flight crew point of view), or they just compute trajectories for one specific emergency. In some cases, the existing solutions are only applied to general aviation. The methodology proposed in this paper tries to bridge all these gaps, producing operationally sound trajectories tailored to specific aircraft (degraded) performance, considering weather and covering a wide range of emergency or urgency situations.

II. BACKGROUND: THE AIRCRAFT TRAJECTORY PREDICTION PROBLEM

In this section, we present the theoretical background needed to generate emergency trajectories with aircraft trajectory prediction algorithms. Other methods could have been used to generate the trajectory, like trajectory optimization; a trade-off analysis between the different methods and techniques available can be found in Section III-A.

Let us divide the aircraft trajectory into N flight phases. For each phase i , defined over the time period $[t_0^{(i)}, t_f^{(i)}]$, a state vector $\mathbf{x}^{(i)}(t)$ and a control vector $\mathbf{u}^{(i)}(t)$ are defined. In this paper, the state vector $\mathbf{x} = [v, h, s, m]$ is composed, respectively, by the true airspeed (TAS), the geometric altitude, the distance to go and the mass of the aircraft; while

the control vector $\mathbf{u} = [T, \gamma, \beta]$ is composed, respectively, by the thrust, the aerodynamic flight path angle and the speed brakes deployment.

The dynamics of \mathbf{x} are expressed by the following set of ordinary differential equations (ODE), which consider a point-mass representation of the aircraft reduced to the well known "gamma-command" model (i.e., vertical equilibrium is assumed):

$$\frac{dv}{dt} = \dot{v} = \frac{T(v, h, \pi) - D(v, h, m, \beta)}{m} - g \sin \gamma \quad (1a)$$

$$\frac{dh}{dt} = \dot{h} = v \sin \gamma \quad (1b)$$

$$\frac{ds}{dt} = \dot{s} = \sqrt{v^2 \cos^2 \gamma - w_x(s, h)^2} + w_s(s, h) \quad (1c)$$

$$\frac{dm}{dt} = \dot{m} = -f(v, h, \pi) \quad (1d)$$

where π is the throttle; D is the aerodynamic drag; w_x and w_s are, respectively, the cross and along path wind components; g is the local gravity acceleration; and f is the total fuel flow.

From an initial aircraft state (\mathbf{x}_0), a trajectory prediction algorithm [9] aims at computing future states, based on the aircraft intent inputs, weather forecast data and an aircraft performance model (APM).

Mathematically, the aircraft intent of each flight phase i could be given as a certain control vector closing the two degrees of freedom of Eq. (1), plus an end condition [10]. In practice, however, aircraft are not operated following specific T and γ profiles, and these controls are not known beforehand. Instead, climbs and descents are typically composed by constant Mach (M), calibrated airspeed (CAS) or energy share factor² (k) segments performed at maximum climb or idle thrust, respectively; while in the cruise phase aircraft typically fly at constant pressure altitude (h_p) and M . Thus, in a generic formulation, two path constraints close the mathematical problem for each phase defining the aircraft trajectory:

$$\mathbf{z}_i(\mathbf{x}(t), \mathbf{u}(t), \mathbf{p}) = 0 \quad (2)$$

For instance, the first path constraint of an hypothetical phase could enforce to fly at constant pressure altitude (i.e., $\dot{h}_p = 0$), while the second one could restrict the CAS to be constant (i.e., $\dot{v}_{CAS} = 0$). In such case, the two parameters defining the pressure altitude and CAS values of the concerned phase must be specified to perform the numerical integration. An excellent description of the different path constraints that could be defined in an ATM context is given in [11].

The dynamics of \mathbf{x} (Eq. 1) together with the two path constraints (Eq. 2) form a system of differential algebraic equations (DAE). Provided that the path constraints are

²For an aircraft that is changing both altitude and speed, the energy share factor specifies how much the available thrust is allocated to the vertical and speed evolution.

meaningful (i.e., they close the mathematical problem), \mathbf{u} can be explicitly determined, reducing the DAE system to an ODE system suitable for numerical integration using standard numerical procedures. The integration is performed until reaching the end condition, which triggers the switch to the following phase.

III. METHODOLOGY

In this section, we present the methodology followed in this work to generate the emergency trajectories by using the formulation detailed in Section II. First of all, in Section III-A, we present a trade-off analysis between several methods and techniques available to generate emergency trajectories. Then, in Section III-B, we give all the details regarding the methodology chosen for this work.

A. Trade-off analysis

In order to tackle the problem presented in this paper, several methods and models are available, each of them with their own strengths and weaknesses. In this section, we highlight the most relevant ones, comparing them and concluding which would be the best approach for the purpose of this work.

1) *Aircraft Performance Model*: The performance of the aircraft is affected by different factors, such as the aircraft weight or the air density. Moreover, the aircraft will perform differently depending on the flight phase being flown (e.g. with the usage of high-lift devices, landing gear, etc.). An APM aims at describing all these behaviors, providing a mathematical description of the motion of an aircraft. An APM should be capable of supporting accurate computation of the geometric, kinematic and kinetic (i.e., dynamic) aspects of the aircraft movement. In addition, it should be applicable to a wide set of aircraft types, over the entire operation flight envelope, and in all phases of flight. Furthermore, it should have a reasonable complexity, maintainability and computing requirements.

At present, there are several existing approaches to aircraft performance modeling. Kinetic approaches model forces, while kinematic approaches directly model the aircraft flight path characteristics without attempting to model the underlying physics. Typical examples of APMs that are used today are introduced and described in [12]. For instance, the GAME model [13] is a kinematic model based on a purely parametric approach; while the base of aircraft data (BADA), developed and maintained by Eurocontrol, follows a kinetic approach [14]. There are other available APMs, like for instance the one offered in PIANO (Project Interactive Analysis and Optimisation), which is an aircraft performance and design software from Lissys Ltd. [15]. None of the currently available performance models, however, are as accurate as the performance data directly derived by aircraft manufacturers, known as original equipment manufacturer (OEM) reference performance data. A large number of flight tests are performed by aircraft manufacturers to identify different performance parameters, and this

data is not typically (or easily) disclosed. In some cases, a real mathematical model is not provided by manufacturers, which provide experimental observations of some flight variables in several different flight regimes, either in tabular or graphical form. Some other manufacturers embed these performance data into performance engineering software tailored to the specific needs of flight dispatchers or airline aircraft performance analysts. Finally, it is worth noting that these performance data are sometimes simplified, and/or surrogate models embedded in FMSs are used. This is due to the fact that FMSs are usually computers with limited computational and memory resources that cannot work with large amounts of data and/or high resolution data.

In this work, we will use the Eurocontrol's base of aircraft data (BADA) v4 [14], which is a widely and recognized APM in the air traffic management community, providing performance models for a large number of aircraft with very accurate results. Although more realistic results could be obtained with the OEM data, given the level of maturity of the presented system, it will not be necessary to have such a level of accuracy in the performance model. BADA will suffice to obtain accurate enough data to produce realistic and representative results, providing some safety buffers are used to account for inaccuracies in the model. Nevertheless, more accurate data would be needed in some cases if the proposed algorithms reach a higher TRL (technology readiness level) and are integrated into a real aircraft platform or simulator. Furthermore, by using OEM data the safety buffers used in our system to account for BADA inaccuracies could be reduced.

2) *Aircraft Dynamics Model*: The motion of an aircraft could be expressed by a 6-degrees-of-freedom (6DoF) model (as depicted in Figure 1) or a 3DoF model, also known as point-mass model:

Fig. 1. 6-degrees-of-freedom model

- **6DoF**: it takes into account both rotational and translational motion. The aircraft can move in three dimensions, on the X, Y and Z axes—i.e., vertical (up and down), lateral (right and left) and longitudinal (forward and backward)—as well as change orientation between those axes through rotation (i.e., pitch, yaw and roll).

- **3DoF/Point-mass model:** a point-mass representation of the aircraft is considered. Only vertical, lateral and longitudinal motion are considered.

The strengths and weaknesses of each model are detailed in Table I.

TABLE I
6DOF AND 3DOF STRENGTHS AND WEAKNESSES

Model	Strengths	Weaknesses
6DoF	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Realistic: the model takes into account all the movements an aircraft could perform • Suitable for handling qualities analysis: this is the preferred model when studying the handling qualities of the aircraft 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Complexity: the system of equations describing the motion of the aircraft is complex, which would complicate the computation of the trajectory.
3DoF / Point-mass model	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Simplicity: this model will simplify the calculations needed to compute the aircraft trajectory. • Suitable for performance analysis: this is the preferred model when studying the performance of the aircraft 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Not realistic for some applications: not all the movements an aircraft could perform are taken into account, so this model may not be suitable for military aircraft or unmanned air vehicles modelling.

The 6DoF model is the most complete model as it takes into account all the movements and rotations an aircraft can perform. However, commercial aircraft trajectories involve small aircraft rotation axes. Furthermore, the angle of sideslip could be considered negligible because of the turn coordinator system that is installed into almost all commercial aircraft. The results of that approximation is the 3DoF model, which considers the aircraft as a point of mass (i.e., point-mass model). Generally, this is the preferred model when studying the performance of an aircraft, while the 6DoF model is used when studying the handling qualities. In this work, the 3DoF/point-mass model will be used.

3) *Trajectory Prediction vs. Trajectory Optimization:* There are two main strategies that could be used in this work to generate emergency trajectories:

- **TP** refers to the process of computing a trajectory given a known sequence of control inputs. From an initial state, a TP algorithm aims at computing future states, based on the flight intent, weather data and an APM. More details regarding TP were explained in Section II.
- **Trajectory Optimization (TO)** formulates the optimization of the aircraft trajectory as an optimal control problem, which aims at finding the best control and parameter vectors that minimize a given cost function. The control inputs are unknowns of the optimization problem. In order to guarantee a feasible and operationally acceptable trajectory, as a result of the optimization, several constraints must be considered. The TO problem can be solved in many different ways, such as with non-linear programming (NLP) solvers.

While both methods could be used to generate trajectories, there are several strengths and weaknesses that should be considered for each of them, as shown in Table II.

TABLE II
TRAJECTORY OPTIMIZATION AND PREDICTION STRENGTHS AND WEAKNESSES

Method	Strengths	Weaknesses
Trajectory Optimization	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Aircraft intents not needed: there is no need to define intents beforehand, the optimizer would be responsible to find the "optimal" intents of the aircraft according to the cost function to be minimized. • Cost function: a great variety of cost functions can be defined, which will lead to several trajectories (e.g. minimize time, minimize drag, maximize flight path angle...) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Convergence: sometimes, the optimizer does not converge and, thus, no trajectory is generated. • Local minima: sometimes the computed trajectory is not the optimal one; instead, the optimizer could find local minima. • Slow: depending on the case and number of phases, the optimizer could take a lot of time to converge.
Trajectory Prediction	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Robust: a trajectory is always generated, there are no convergence problems (numerical integration). • Fast: the solution is found in a short time (< 10s). 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Definition of intents: the aircraft intents need to be known and defined beforehand. • Initial state and Forward/Backward integration: the initial state of the aircraft has to be known.

In this work, the trajectory will be generated by means of a TP. Due to the fact that we are generating emergency trajectories, it is of high importance that a trajectory is always found, which cannot be ensured with TO techniques. In addition, TP techniques can produce results way faster than TO techniques, which in some situations could take a lot of time to converge to an optimal solution. Therefore, although it might be more complex to define the set of intents that define the emergency trajectory, TP is the trajectory generation technique chosen in this work.

4) *Automation vs. Pilot Interaction:* In Table III, the strengths and weaknesses of a system focused on automation vs. a system focusing on pilot interaction are shown. Note the fact that in any case our framework must provide at least one emergency trajectory that ensures the aircraft will safely arrive at a landing site.

While an automation-focused system might seem better for an emergency scenario, our objective is to increase the interaction with the pilot, with certain limits. If a fully-automated system were designed, the totality of emergency situations should be taken into account. Apart from the obvious difficulty when defining all the cases (and the great amount of cases that we should consider), in such a situation the pilot would not be able to interact at all with the system. And, due to the inherent uncertain nature of emergency situations, it might be advisable to allow the pilot to interact with the system after assessing the current situation.

TABLE III
AUTOMATION AND PILOT INTERACTION STRENGTHS AND WEAKNESSES

	Strengths	Weaknesses
Automation	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • One trajectory for each emergency: for each possible emergency situation, the system generates one single trajectory that will lead the aircraft safely to a landing site. • Low pilot workload: the pilot does not need to interact with the system, he/she just needs to follow the generated trajectory. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • All emergency cases should be considered: there is a great amount of emergencies that could happen, and the system should be able to take them all into account. However, during an emergency, a lot of unexpected events could occur, which will make hard to define the totality of cases that the system should consider. • The pilot cannot decide: the pilot cannot give an input to the system.
Pilot interaction	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Set of trajectories: a set of trajectories per landing site will be given, the pilot can choose which one to fly after assessing the emergency situation. • Pilot inputs: the pilot will be able to assess the current emergency situation and give proper inputs to the system (e.g., use of speed brakes). 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • High pilot workload: the pilot needs to interact with the system, which will increase his/her workload. • Not suitable for time-critical emergencies: when time is the limiting factor (e.g., fire on board), it would be advisable to limit the level of interaction with the pilot.

In any case, the proposed system will still compute trajectories that would safely bring the aircraft to a landing site. However, the pilot, after assessing the existing emergency, will be able to choose among a set of trajectories, as usually there will be more than one possible trajectory per landing site. Furthermore, the pilot will be able to input certain “parameters” to the system, such as the use of speed brakes.

B. Motion Planner

In this work, the framework in charge of generating the emergency trajectory is known as the motion planner. This framework uses a given route, together with the current aircraft performance and weather (i.e., temperature, pressure and wind) to generate an emergency trajectory linking the aircraft position with a given landing site. Different predefined vertical profiles are considered in the motion planner and each one is considered independently. Given a triggering event (i.e., emergency situation for a particular scenario), a profile from this predetermined catalogue is automatically chosen by the tool and the corresponding emergency trajectory is computed. It is worth noting that these pre-computed profiles are not given in terms of trajectories, but as a sequence of aircraft intents, tailored to each case.

The set of vertical profiles (Table IV) considered in this work have been designed to be as generic as possible in order to cover the widest possible range of emergency situations. However, most of emergencies are aircraft model dependent, so the procedure described in each aircraft’s FCOM would ultimately affect the definition of the vertical profiles.

In this work, the TP logic implemented in the motion planner considers the following aspects:

- **Trajectory phases:** the vertical profile of the aircraft trajectory is split in a finite number of phases. Each phase is specified by an end condition and two aircraft intents.
- **Aircraft intents:** operational intents, similar to those one could find in state-of-the-art FMSs, such as flying at constant Mach, CAS, altitude, throttle setting, flight path angle, etc.
- **End condition:** needed to define the transition from one phase to the other where intents might change and/or aerodynamic conditions might change (i.e., usage of flaps, landing gear, etc). Example: a phase is flown at constant Mach and Idle thrust (2 intents) until the moment the CAS achieves a given value (end condition of the phase given in terms of CAS); then, the next phase is flown at constant CAS and constant vertical speed (2 different intents).
- **Trajectory computation:** a trajectory is unequivocally specified given a sequence of phases, with the 2 intents per phase and the end condition specified. This allows to close the 2 degrees of freedom of the mathematical model describing the movement of the aircraft in the vertical plane (i.e., numerically integrate the equations of movement).

The list of profiles, including how the trajectory is computed in each case are fixed by the motion planner and the pilot will not be able to change them. However, in some cases, more than one outcome could be presented by default to the pilot, who could select the desired trajectory. Moreover, for some phases, the pilot could request the system to change the values for (some of) the intents. For instance, in a Mach descent, the pilot could decide the value for Mach, but could not replace that phase for a CAS descent, for instance.

The output of the motion planner component is a trajectory plan. Then, this plan will have to be executed in flight by the (auto) pilot. In nominal operations, the FMS of the aircraft also computes this kind of trajectory plan. A typical example would be the aircraft descent, in where the top of descent (TOD) is fixed. This plan becomes the guidance command for the autopilot, which will try to follow the plan (in managed mode) and adjust the aircraft controls to compensate for uncertainty (mainly due to inaccuracies in the weather forecast and to a lesser extent, inaccuracies in the aircraft performance).

Although the aircraft crew is responsible for deploying speed brakes, high-lift devices (i.e., flaps/slats) and landing

gear at the moment they consider the most appropriate, a descent plan computed by a FMS makes some hypotheses on the moments these devices will be deployed. In this work, the same philosophy is followed, taking into account that the descent trajectory is not computed until the runway threshold, but down to a predefined point in space that depends on the type of emergency, health of the aircraft and characteristics of the landing site. Thus, some hypotheses are made regarding the usage of speed brakes, flap/slats and landing gear, which are specified in each profile definition. The vertical profiles considered in this work depend on the following factors:

- **Engines available:** total engine flame out (TEFO) or at least one engine is operative.
- **Type of emergency:** Land as soon as possible (ASAP, e.g., fire on cabin) or at the nearest suitable airport (ANSA, e.g. depressurization in cabin).
- **Approach procedure:** airport with or without a suitable instrumental flight rules (IFR) approach procedure.
- **Maneuverability:** aircraft fully or not fully maneuverable.

In addition to these factors, in case no engines are available, the availability of fuel on board is also considered. The combination of these factors, taking into account that some combinations for the TEFO cases lead to the same profile, gives as a result the list of profiles of Table IV.

TABLE IV
LIST OF PROFILES

Profile #	Engines available	Type of emergency	IFR	Maneuverability	Fuel on board
1 ³	No	ASAP	-	-	Yes
2 ³	No	ASAP	-	-	No
3	Yes	ASAP	Yes	Yes	Yes
4	Yes	ASAP	Yes	No	Yes
5	Yes	ASAP	No	Yes	Yes
6	Yes	ASAP	No	No	Yes
7	Yes	ANSA	Yes	Yes	Yes
8	Yes	ANSA	Yes	No	Yes
9	Yes	ANSA	No	Yes	Yes
10	Yes	ANSA	No	No	Yes
11 ⁴	Yes	ANSA	-	-	Yes

IV. RESULTS

In this Section, we show the results obtained in this work. In Section IV-A, we describe the scenario and we explain the inputs needed to apply our methodology. Then, in Section IV-B, we describe the case-studies. Finally, in Section IV-C, we show the computed trajectories.

³ Regardless of the availability of an IFR approach procedure and regardless of the maneuverability status of the aircraft. Note that big aircraft relying on hydraulic power are not fully maneuverable without engine power.

⁴Depressurization or smoke in cabin. For the last part of this emergency trajectory, the aircraft intents from Profiles 7 to 10 are used.

A. Scenario Description and Inputs

The scenario considered in this paper is depicted in a simplified way in Figure 2. We assume that an Airbus A320 is cruising at FL360, with a speed equal to Mach 0.78 and at a distance of 112NM from a given suitable landing site when an emergency happens. At this moment, a trajectory is generated that safely brings the aircraft from the cruise phase (where the emergency happens) to a given *final point* (which will depend on the emergency type) close to the landing site. In this paper, we assume that a 2D path (i.e., route) that avoids all the obstacles in the way is given. The task of generating this route was described in [1].

Fig. 2. Scenario

In order to successfully generate emergency trajectories, the following inputs are needed:

- **APM:** in this work, we use BADA v4. For all case-studies, an Airbus A320-232 has been used.
- **Weather data:** in this work, the longitudinal component of the wind is modelled by a smoothing spline [16], $w: \mathbb{R} \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$, such that:

$$w(h) = \sum_{i=1}^{n_c} c_i B_i(h), \quad (3)$$

where B_i , $i = 1, \dots, n_c$ are the B-spline basis functions and $\mathbf{c} = [c_1, \dots, c_{n_c}]$ are the control points of the smoothing spline.

It should be noted that the longitudinal wind has been modelled as a function of the altitude only, as done in similar works [17]. The control points of the spline approximating the longitudinal wind profile are obtained by fitting historical weather data. This data is obtained from gridded binary (GRIB) formatted files provided by the global forecast system (GFS) of the National Oceanic and Atmospheric Administration (NOAA) [18]. Apart from the wind, this data is used as well to obtain the values for temperature and pressure as a function of altitude. In this work, weather data in Frankfurt Airport at 12pm for July, 25, 2018 was used to conduct the experiments.

B. Case-Studies

From the list of profiles in Table IV, 4 profiles were selected in this work: profile 1, 2, 3 and 7. For profile 7,

TABLE V
PROFILE 1: TEFO + ASAP + FUEL ON BOARD

Phase	a/c intent #1		a/c intent #2	
(Above FL200) Deceleration/acceleration to relight speed	ALT	Current altitude	THR	IDLE
CAS descent	CAS	Relight speed	THR	IDLE
(Below FL200) Deceleration to green dot	ALT	Current altitude	THR	IDLE
CAS descent	CAS	Green dot	THR	IDLE
Acceleration to increase rate of descent	ACC	-	THR	IDLE
Descent at higher speed to increase rate of descent	CAS	CAS_n	THR	IDLE
Deceleration to V_{app}	DEC	-	THR	IDLE

TABLE VII
PROFILE 3: ENGINE(S) OPERATIVE + ASAP + IFR + FULLY MANEUVERABLE

Phase	a/c intent #1		a/c intent #2	
Acceleration to descent Mach	ACC	-	THR	IDLE
Mach descent	MACH	MMO	THR	IDLE
Flight at crossover altitude	CAS	VMO	ALT	Crossover altitude
CAS descent	CAS	VMO	THR	IDLE
Deceleration to V_{F1}	DEC	-	THR	IDLE
Level-off to intercept FAP/FAF	CAS	V_{F1}	ALT	FAP/FAF altitude

TABLE IX
PROFILE 7B: ENGINE(S) OPERATIVE + ANSA + IFR + FULLY MANEUVERABLE (WITH INITIAL ACCELERATION TO MMO)

Phase	a/c intent #1		a/c intent #2	
Acceleration to higher Mach	ALT	Current altitude	THR	MCT
Cruise	MACH	MMO	ALT	Current altitude
Mach descent	MACH	MMO	THR	IDLE
CAS descent	CAS	CAS_x	THR	IDLE
Deceleration to V_{F1}	DEC	-	THR	IDLE

two versions were considered. Tables V, VI, VII, VIII and IX contain, respectively, the trajectory phases and aircraft intents for each profile. The different aircraft intents that appear in these tables are the following: ALT, maintain a constant altitude; MACH, maintain a constant Mach number; CAS, maintain a constant CAS; ACC: accelerate at a given acceleration or with a given load factor; DEC, decelerate at a given deceleration or with a given load factor; THR: keep a given throttle setting. For the ACC and DEC cases, we have used the energy share factor value proposed by BADA [14], which varies for acceleration and deceleration and depends on the flight phase (descent or climb). More details for each profile are given below:

- **Profiles 1 and 2 (Dual-engine failure):** these two profiles (Tables V and VI) assume a dual-engine failure, which leads to a total loss of thrust (as the aircraft considered is a twin-engine aircraft, an A320). If there is no fuel on board (profile 2), the aircraft flies at the recommended speed for maximum range (green dot

TABLE VI
PROFILE 2: TEFO + ASAP + NO FUEL ON BOARD

Phase	a/c intent #1		a/c intent #2	
Deceleration to green dot	ALT	Current altitude	THR	IDLE
CAS descent	CAS	Green dot	THR	IDLE
Acceleration to increase rate of descent	ACC	-	THR	IDLE
Descent at higher speed to increase rate of descent	CAS	CAS_n	THR	IDLE
Deceleration to V_{app}	DEC	-	THR	IDLE

TABLE VIII
PROFILE 7A: ENGINE(S) OPERATIVE + ANSA + IFR + FULLY MANEUVERABLE (CURRENT SPEED AND ALTITUDE)

Phase	a/c intent #1		a/c intent #2	
Cruise	MACH	Current Mach	ALT	Current altitude
Mach descent	MACH	Current Mach	THR	IDLE
CAS descent	CAS	CAS_x	THR	IDLE
Deceleration to V_{F1}	DEC	-	THR	IDLE

speed⁵) until being sure to “make” the best landing site available. Once this is ensured, speed may be increased (to a certain CAS value, CAS_n) to increase rate of descent if necessary. Then, a final deceleration should deliver the aircraft in landing configuration at V_{app} —approach speed, which is the final approach speed when the flaps/slats are in landing configuration and the landing gear is extended—on a 650ft/Nm glide path, and at least 5NM before touchdown area. If there is fuel on board (profile 1) and the aircraft is above FL200, first an acceleration or deceleration (depending on the initial speed) to the relight speed will be performed. This speed will be maintained until FL200, where the aircraft will decelerate to green dot.

- **Profile 3 (ASAP with engine(s) operative):** this emergency could correspond, for instance, to a fire on board situation. The set of trajectory phases and intents are found in Table VII. The aircraft follows an MMO/VMO (maximum operating Mach/maximum operating CAS) profile until the final deceleration to V_{F1} , which is the target speed for flaps deployed in configuration 1. Finally, a level-off at V_{F1} and at the FAP/FAF (final approach point/final approach fix) is performed to intercept the ILS (instrumental landing system). Depending on the distance to the landing site, the aircraft will fly for a given distance at the crossover altitude, where TAS is maximized (i.e, aircraft flies at both MMO

⁵For the Airbus A320, the green dot speed is the minimum operating speed in managed mode and clean configuration, being approximately the best lift-to-drag ratio speed.

Fig. 3. Baseline trajectories

and VMO).

- **Profiles 7A and 7B (ANSA):** this emergency could correspond, for instance, to a fuel leak emergency when the aircraft is in cruise. The set of phases and intents considered in this case are described in Tables VIII and IX corresponding, respectively, to profiles 7A and 7B. For profile 7A, it is assumed that the aircraft keeps its current (cruise) speed and altitude. Then, a typical Mach/CAS descent (cruise Mach and a certain CAS, CAS_x) is performed until reaching the IAF (initial approach fix), with the aircraft aligned with the initial approach segment and at V_{F1} . Even if the emergency is ANSA, it might be desirable to arrive earlier to the landing site to minimize the possibility of incurring into a worse emergency. One option would be to fly a profile similar to the ASAP case, where the aircraft flies at the crossover altitude in order to maximize TAS. Another option would be the one considered in profile 7B, where an initial acceleration to MMO is performed when the aircraft is in the cruise phase.

As discussed in Section III-B, the pilot could request the system to change the values for some of the intents. In this work, we also show the resulting trajectories when the descent CAS value for profile 2 is changed. Moreover, we will also show the effect that the distance to go (i.e., the distance to the landing site) has on the emergency trajectories for profile 2. The resulting trajectories for all case-studies are shown in Section IV-C.

C. Final Trajectories

Figure 3 shows the resulting trajectories for the profiles specified in Section IV-B. The evolution of the speed and altitude for each profile is shown. In addition, the red and black dashed lines correspond, respectively, to MMO and VMO.

Profiles 1 and 2 (Figures 3(a) and 3(b)) correspond to a TEFO emergency with and without fuel on board, respectively. In profile 1, we can observe that above FL200 the aircraft flies at a higher CAS—corresponding to the reflight speed—than in profile 2. This involves a higher rate of descent than in profile 2. Below FL200, aircraft decelerates to green dot, which involves a decrease in the rate of descent. Finally, in both profiles, there is an acceleration to VMO after the green dot section in order to increase the rate of descent, which is needed to ensure the landing site is reached. Finally, in order to ensure the aircraft arrives with the right energy state to the final point of the trajectory, a deceleration to V_{app} is performed.

Figure 3(c) corresponds to the emergency trajectory for profile 3, corresponding to an ASAP situation. As the aim is to arrive the earliest possible to the landing site, the aircraft first accelerates to MMO while descending. The descent continues until the crossover altitude, when reaching VMO. At this altitude, the TAS is maximized. Then, the aircraft flies at this constant altitude until being close to the airport. At that moment, another descent is performed at VMO, until the final deceleration to V_{F1} .

Finally, Figures 3(d) and 3(e) correspond to profiles 7A

Fig. 4. Profile 2 (TEFO with no fuel on board) with different distances to go

Fig. 5. Profile 2 (TEFO with no fuel on board) with different descent CAS values

and 7B, respectively. The trajectories are very similar, except for the initial acceleration to MMO that can be observed for Profile 7B during the cruise phase. Then, in both cases, the aircraft follows a Mach/CAS profile. For profile 7A, it is a Mach 0.78/CAS 300 kt trajectory while for profile 7B it is a Mach 0.82/CAS 300 kt trajectory. At the end of the trajectory, a deceleration to V_{F1} is performed in both cases.

Figure 4 shows the effect of the distance to go in the emergency trajectory for profile 2. For the baseline conditions (Figure 4(b)), when the landing site is located at 112NM, the aircraft decelerates to the green dot speed until being closer to the landing site, when it accelerates to a higher CAS, as it was discussed earlier in this section. However, if the landing site is closer, for instance at 70NM from the aircraft, the resulting vertical profile will be different, as depicted in Figure 4(a). In such a case, there would be no need to fly at green dot speed, as the airport could be reached by simply flying an MMO/VMO profile, followed by the final deceleration to V_{app} . Furthermore, if the airport is closer than 70NM, the route followed by the aircraft in that case would involve flying a certain number of spirals in order to lose the required altitude to ensure the landing site is reached.

On the other hand, if the landing site is further than 112NM, the aircraft will need to fly for a longer time at green dot. The limiting case is depicted in Figure 4(c), corresponding to the case where the landing site is located at 127NM from the aircraft. This distance corresponds to the

maximum range that the aircraft can achieve for the given emergency and under the weather conditions considered for this experiment.

Figure 5 shows the effect of changing the descent CAS value for profile 2 (CAS_n in Table VI). Depending on the specific conditions and depending on the pilot, the CAS used to increase the rate of descent in order to reach the landing site might be different. It is important to remark the fact that the 3 trajectories depicted in Figure 5 ensure that the aircraft will safely reach the landing site. However, the lower the CAS, the shorter the section where the aircraft is flying at the green dot speed. In addition, lower values of CAS allow to fly a less steep flight profile, which might be more desirable for some pilots. Additionally, it might be also better to not force the aircraft to fly at VMO during an emergency. Still, these decisions will ultimately depend on each aircraft's FCOM guidelines.

Regarding the computational time, the motion planner takes between 2 to 5 seconds to generate a trajectory, depending on the profile considered. Still, we are still using a very simple prototype to test our concept; in the future, we expect to optimize our code, as well as to run the tests in a more powerful computer or server.

V. CONCLUSIONS

In this work, we showed a novel methodology to generate trajectory plans for emergency situations, designed to safely lead the aircraft to a designated landing site. For that

purpose, we defined a set of vertical profiles with associated trajectory phases and aircraft intents. Then, a TP algorithm was used to generate the emergency trajectories.

We showed that we are capable of generating emergency trajectories for a wide range of emergency situations in a short amount of time (less than 5 seconds). Ultimately, the concept presented in this paper aims to be part of an in-flight support tool for the FMS. The trajectory plans, after being injected in the FMS, would be executed in-flight by the (auto) pilot.

This work focuses only on the generation of the vertical profile of the trajectory; in [1], more details regarding the route generation were given. Furthermore, in the future, an insight on the landing site selection process will be given, and a wider range of situations will be investigated in order to assess the feasibility of our concept.

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REFERENCES

- [1] R. Sáez, H. Khaledian, X. Prats, A. Guitart, D. Delahaye, and E. Feron. A Fast and Flexible Emergency Trajectory Generator-Enhancing Emergency Geometric Planning with Aircraft Dynamics. In Proceedings of the 14th USA/Europe Air Traffic Management Research and Development Seminar (ATM2021), 2021.
- [2] E. M. Atkins, I. A. Portillo, and M. J. Strube. Emergency Flight Planning Applied to Total Loss of Thrust. Journal of Aircraft, 43(4), 2006.
- [3] E. M. Atkins. Emergency landing automation aids: an evaluation inspired by US airways flight 1549. In AIAA Infotech@Aerospace Conference, Atlanta, Georgia, USA, 2010.
- [4] P. F. Di Donato and E. M. Atkins. An Off-Runway Emergency Landing Aid for a Small Aircraft Experiencing Loss of Thrust. In AIAA Infotech@Aerospace Conference, Kissimmee, Florida, USA, 2015.
- [5] S. Paul, F. Hole, A. Zytek, and C. A. Varela. Flight Trajectory Planning for Fixed-Wing Aircraft in Loss of Thrust Emergencies. In Second International Conference on InfoSymbiotics/DDDAS(Dynamic Data Driven Applications Systems), MIT, Cambridge, Massachusetts, USA, 2017.
- [6] N. Meuleau, C. Plaunt, E. D. Smith, and T. Smith. An emergency landing planner for damaged aircraft. In 21st Conference on Innovative Applications of Artificial Intelligence, Pasadena, California, USA, 2009.
- [7] M. Miwa, T. Takeshi, Y. Satoshi, T. Nobuhiro, and S. Shinji. Real-Time Trajectory Generation Applicable to Emergency Landing Approach. The Japan Society for Aeronautical and Space Sciences, 52(175):21—28, 2009.
- [8] Garmin Ltd. Autonomi™Autonomous Safety-enhancing Technologies. <https://discover.garmin.com/en-US/autonomi/>, 2021. Accessed: 2021-04-02.
- [9] Ramon Dalmau, Marc Melgosa, Santi Vilardaga, and Xavier Prats. A Fast and Flexible Aircraft Trajectory Predictor and Optimiser for ATM Research Applications. In Proceedings of the 8th International Congress on Research in Air Transportation (ICRAT), Castelldefels, Catalonia, Jun 2018. Eurocontrol and FAA.
- [10] D. González-Arribas, M. Soler, J. López-Leonés, E. Casado, and Sanjurjo-Rivo M. Automated optimal flight planning based on the aircraft intent description language. Proceedings of the Institution of Mechanical Engineers, Part G: Journal of Aerospace Engineering, 233(3), 2018.
- [11] E. Gallo, J. Lopez-Leones, and M. Vilaplana. Trajectory computation infrastructure based on BADA aircraft performance model. In 26th AIAA/IEEE Digital Avionics Systems Conference Proceedings, Dallas, Texas, USA, Jun 2007.
- [12] A. Suchkov, S. Swierstra, and A. Nuic. Aircraft performance modeling for air traffic management applications. In Proceedings of the 5th USA/Europe Air Traffic Management Research and Development Seminar, Hungary, 2003. Eurocontrol and FAA.
- [13] P. Calders. GAME-Model Conventions, Eurocontrol Document, 2000.
- [14] Eurocontrol. User Manual for the Base of Aircraft Data (BADA) Family 4, 2014.
- [15] Lyssys Ltd. Piano. <https://www.lyssys.uk/index.html#find>, 2020. Accessed: 2020-04-29.
- [16] Carl de Boor. On calculating with B-splines. Journal of Approximation Theory, 6(1):50–62, 1972.
- [17] Raúl Sáez, Xavier Prats, Tatiana Polishchuk, and Valentin Polishchuk. Traffic Synchronization in Terminal Airspace to Enable Continuous Descent Operations in Trombone Sequencing and Merging Procedures: An Implementation Study for Frankfurt Airport. Transportation Research Part C: Emerging Technologies, 121, 2020.
- [18] National Oceanic and Atmospheric Administration (NOAA). Global Forecast System (GFS). <https://www.ncdc.noaa.gov/data-access/model-data/model-datasets/global-forecast-system-gfs>, 2021. Accessed: 2021-01-22.